

FORMING A SENSE OF NATIONAL IDENTITY IN STUDENTS

Ra'no Rizayeva

Deputy head of Family and Women's Management

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646526>

Having a national feeling is extremely important in understanding national identity. National feeling is the basis for speaking the national language, thinking in the context of the national way of life, operating within the norms that serve as the main standard in the organization of socio-national relations.

A person who does not have a national feeling cannot define his subjective position as a person or a representative of a nation, he is alien to the notions of national pride and honor. Consequently, only an understanding of national identity allows the factors that have become a value for the nation to take precedence in the life of society. Therefore, the formation of a sense of national identity in young people, including adolescents, in educational institutions, the creation of the need to preserve national identity is of particular importance and poses important challenges to the science of pedagogy.

Having a sense of national identity during the school years lays the foundation for the young generation to grow up to be true patriots. The science of pedagogy has great potential in students' understanding of national identity.

After all, it is about the ancestral example of the younger generation, national values and national way of life. Students' sense of national identity not only ensures the development of society, but also helps them to grow into a fully developed, mature person.

Therefore, the understanding of national identity, the need to reveal its content and essence from a pedagogical point of view, using the opportunities provided by independence, is a topical issue today.

Thus, the understanding of national identity "Understanding that each nation (ethnic group) is a real existing entity, representing certain material and spiritual wealth, a common language, customs and traditions, values and belonging to the state, common interests and needs", "ethnic group", the role of peoples and nations in their relations, their rights in social life. The process of achieving national freedom, spiritual and political dignity and ensuring it in practice.

-Achieve a strong unity of knowledge, skills and abilities about spiritual life, national heritage, traditions and customs, values, psyche, consciously evaluate them, achieve a positive assessment of spiritual feelings, conscious self-government, living with a sense of homeland, its a set of qualities such as

contributing to the development of the country, respect for the mother tongue and respect for other nations. It is a deep understanding of what is going on.

At present, another important process of awakening is taking place in our country, so the words “New Uzbekistan” and “Third Renaissance” resonate in our lives and inspire our people to great goals. In one of the hadiths collected by Imam Bukhari, it is said: “Knowledge learned in youth is like a pattern carved in stone”.

It is well known from history that our great scholars, following such wisdom, made great discoveries in the field of science and made an invaluable contribution to the development of thinking in general. Continuing such sacred traditions, it is not only our duty, but also our sacred duty to history and the future to bring up new Khorezmians, Ferganais, Berunis, Ibn Sina, Mirzo Ulugbeks and Navoi in our country.

Awareness of national identity:

- ☐ a deep understanding of the past, history and development of the nation to which it belongs;
- ☐ respect for its language and national-ethnic features;
- ☐ feeling the need to be educated in the spirit of national customs, traditions, values and culture;
- ☐ pride in the nation's contribution to human civilization;
- ☐ to understand that the specificity of the national-social way of life is one of the important features of the nation;
- ☐ to understand that the symbols of nationality and state independence (state flag, coat of arms, anthem) are the determining factors of the honor, glory, pride and dignity of the nation;
- ☐ to properly assess the role and prestige of the nation in the international arena, to express confidence in its present and future;
- ☐ in the process of socio-national relations, it means achieving equal cooperation with other nations and peoples.

These circumstances are the criteria that determine the degree to which an individual has a sense of national identity.

List of used literature:

1. Karimov I.A. Harmoniously developed generation – the basis of development of Uzbekistan. T. “Sharq” Publishing and Printing Concern. 1997. pp 319.
2. Karimov I.A. Let the ideology of our society serve to make the people – the people, the nation – the nation. “Tafakkur” journal. 1998. №2-3. pp 2-16.

3. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. T. "Spirituality". 2008. pp 27.
4. Mirziyoev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan is becoming a country of democratic change, wide opportunities and practical work. T. "Teacher". 2021. pp 11.

